

PUBLIC RELATIONS OF A GENERAL EDUCATION INSTITUTION AS A FACTOR OF SCHOOL IMAGE FORMATION

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Abstract. *Development of science and technology also creates new requirements and demands in the field of education. It is not surprising that a number of reforms in the system of public education are being carried out on modern generation of young generation, the organization of educational process with modern conditions. At the same time, the development of educational institutions, their role and status in society is of great importance.*

Keywords: *science and technology, education, reforms, public education system, modern teaching technologies, educational institutions, competition, international experience.*

Introduction. The development of science and technology creates new needs and demands in the field of education. It is not for nothing that a number of reforms are being carried out in the public education system regarding the modern technologies of teaching the young generation, the organization of the educational process with modern conditions. At this point, the development of educational institutions, increasing their place and position in society is becoming more and more important. It is possible to find a solution to the above-mentioned issues by organizing the effective activities of educational institutions, looking for ways to increase the environment of healthy competition between them, and studying international experience and mechanisms of creating a modern school image. After all, with the development of healthy competition in the market of educational services, the quality and efficiency of education is achieved.

PR (PR is an English word that means "public relations", "relationships with the public") in the formation of the image of a general educational institution. The international Webster's dictionary describes the purpose and function of PR as follows: "RR - it is the creation of mutual sincerity and mutual understanding of individuals and organizations with other people, groups and society as a whole, as well as the distribution of explanatory and analytical articles, the development of information exchange, and the assessment of public opinion and influence. Public relations-RR (public relations) is a technology of creating and implementing the image of a certain object in socio-economic and political systems. Ideas, goods, services, individuals, organizations, firms, brands form an important aspect of this technology. PR in a broad sense means management of public opinion, establishment of relations between society and state agencies or commercial structures, promotion of positive competition, including unbiased understanding of social, political or economic processes)¹ problems can be solved and problems can be prevented. Because it is important to study how effectively the institution is operating through the attitude of its public. Also, every process in the activity of the educational institution, teaching, paid educational services, spiritual events, students' lives, achievements, pedagogical community environment, pedagogues' skills and achievements, parents' demands and the attitude of public representatives

towards the institution will definitely affect the prestige, rating and is considered a factor that serves to ensure competitiveness.

When organizing PR activities of a general education institution,

- establishing various information channels that increase interest in the educational institution and its educational services;
- to attract public attention to increase the reputation and rating level of the educational institution;
- It is intended to achieve the formation of trust in the activities of the educational institution by public representatives, parents, teaching staff and students.

Of course, the main community of general education schools is made up of parents of students, those who express interest in the educational process and applicants of educational services, students. It is important for them to establish PR activities of the school [1]:

- about the educational program implemented by the educational institution;
- about the cost of additional education services;
- about rare pedagogues and unique conditions;
- about the educational process of the educational institution;
- about the psychological environment of the institution;
- a lot of information of interest to the public of the institution, such as major projects and successes of pedagogues and students, is provided.

The relevance of the topic is that in the formation of the image of secondary schools, the establishment of the PR activity of the institution, developing the appearance of a competitive school, a modern school; It is intended to develop the main role and place of the school in the continuous education system by developing the interaction between the school and its community. Also, the purpose of research, formation of the image of the educational institution and maintaining its status is to show its image and status in the eyes of society, participants of the educational system, parents, social institutions, employers, and all people interested in educational activities, to maintain and develop it.

It is possible to cite researches of a number of scientists on the issue of setting up the PR activity of a general educational institution. Nizhegorod Institute of Educational Development, Dean of the Faculty of Educational Management and Economics, Candidate of Economic Sciences Vifleemskiy Anatoliy Borisovich "PR technologies in education", REU named after G.V. Plekhanova, Master of the Department of Foreign Languages Larionova Darya Sergeevna entitled "Specific PR-technological and educational sphere", public educational institution secondary school No. 380, "Organization of PR activities of an educational institution in the external environment" by Olga Nikolaevna Agunovich, deputy director of educational affairs, music teacher Koval Tatyana Eduardovna "Types of PR activities in the management of a municipal educational institution", Orlov State Institute of Trade and Economics, Graduate student of "Advertising and Public Relations" Yu.V.Solomon's scientific articles entitled "PR-technologies in the educational sphere"(and many similar) scientific views on the PR activities of the educational institution are described.

Also, the scientists of our country conducted research on topics such as PR activity, PR activity of the organization. For example, Eshbekov Tolkin Usmonovich "Information service: theory and practice" training manual book (Tashkent. NUUZ -2015), Ya. Mamatova, S. Sulaymonova. "Uzbekistan on the road to development of media education", educational manual (UNESCO) can be cited as an example.

However, not much research has been conducted on the criteria for creating the image of a general education institution, on the formation of school PR activities. Researching this topic, analyzing existing scientific materials, finding solutions to the existing problems in the public education system and the activities of general education schools today, studying and implementing ways to raise the status of the school in society, and developing competitiveness among general education institutions represent the main goal and scientific innovation of the topic.

It is not a secret that the position of general education institutions is slightly declining due to some problems arising in general education schools, violations among students, the quality and efficiency of education is not up to the required level, and the information that parents want their children to receive quality education and are getting answers to these requirements from non-state educational institutions is not a secret today. -we can also observe that it is playing in the ear. It's like a law in economics: demand creates supply, and we can point to the growing number of private educational institutions as an example. If the participants of the market of educational services can be called as competitors, then it is possible to analyze the activities of state, non-state general education institutions, secondary special and higher education institutions. In the organization of the educational process, not only the combination of subjects, but also the curriculum, the organization of educational activities and, as one of the important aspects, issues such as the level of the spiritual and psychological environment of the educational institution are taken into account. The development of internal interaction within PR events and activities helps to form the identity of the educational institution. Therefore, the use of PR technologies in the activities of educational institutions is important, but it can be said that until now, this issue has not been sufficiently studied and implemented in the public education system of our country.

Services in the field of education are different from the field of material production. This affects the establishment and development of PR activity. The provision of intangible products, that is, educational services, represents the marketing sphere of the institution's activity. If we consider advertising as a familiar activity for all educational institutions, then the use of PR-technologies is usually "know-how"². Of course, the need for financial support cannot be ignored as a necessary factor for conducting PR activities³ for educational institutions. But the use of PR technologies in an educational institution requires much less capital than in the areas of material production. Therefore, the use of PR-technologies is not only useful, but also helps to increase the image of the educational institution.

It should be mentioned that PR activities are more or less used in any educational institution. Even so, the announcements made within the framework of the holding of large and small events are, so to speak, in the form of advertisements. However, this situation is insufficient for the development and effective functioning of the institution [1]. O

The strategic plan and management activities of the institution should be reflected in the basis of the use of PR activities. The challenging aspect of this activity for the head of the institution can be explained as follows: firstly, the educational institution must provide quality educational services, and secondly, it will be necessary to increase its sources of income by expanding additional educational services (in the form of marketing of educational services).

In organizing each activity, it is necessary to pay attention to specific aspects, to avoid allowing one activity to interfere with another activity. The use of PR activities can be an effective way to ensure the success of the educational services provided by the educational institution, that

is, the first task is to achieve the school's own brand in the market of the offered educational services.

If we take private educational institutions as an example (it is known that the competition between private educational institutions is significantly strong), they can observe the following actions to strengthen their brand in the market of educational services:

- meeting all requirements for business (financial, material and intangible resources) in the market of quality educational services;
- development and implementation of new educational projects;
- strengthening the position in the market of educational services as the demands of consumers of educational services increase;
- expansion of opportunities to find extra-budgetary funds⁴.

The brand that the educational institution creates for the public should be created for itself first, that is, by having its own way to achieve the quality and efficiency of the provided educational services. It is observed that the services provided as a brand are not as advertised, creating an "anti-brand" situation, as a result of which the public's trust is lost (it is difficult to restore it). So, what does it take to create a worthy brand for an educational institution? In fact, the brand technology for creating tangible goods is not so different from creating a brand for an educational institution. It can be said that, despite the fact that this process lasts a little longer, the educational institution requires a number of marketing activities to be completed, in particular:

- To maintain competitive quality educational services (goods) taking into account the demands of consumers, despite the changing demands of consumers and the educational services offered by competing educational institutions.

- Creating attributes specific to the educational institution (for example, the name of the institution, logo, unique image, etc.). At the same time, the relevant aspects for participants in the institution's activities, the proximity of the institution to the residence, the comfort and hygienic cleanliness of the institution, the friendliness of the staff, the uniqueness of the lesson schedule, the curriculum, as well as the "inter-institutional reputation", the reputation and rating of the school in the given area, should be created. At the same time, the development of a system of PR activities with the establishment of necessary public relations [1].

In general, we can continue a lot of scientific and practical thoughts on the study and research of the PR activity of a general educational institution, and now, in this regard, it can be said that PR is a supporting factor in the process of strategic work of the institution today and tomorrow, a system representing purposeful action.

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